

Assessment of SIMULATE5-K Core-only Model against SIMULATE-3K for KKL Transients

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this research is to evaluate the performance of the Leibstadt nuclear reactor (KKL) SIMULATE5-K (S5K) core-only model against the already established SIMULATE-3K (S3K) code and plant's reference model. To this end, representative limiting transients for KKL were analyzed, with accuracy assessed based on the level of agreement with S3K results under a range of operating conditions. As an initial step, the S3K model, including both core and peripherals, was used to generate boundary conditions for the S5K calculations, applying two hydraulic schemes: PRES-PRES (PP), specifying inlet and outlet pressures, and FLOW-PBAL (FP), specifying inlet flow and outlet pressure. Both S5K schemes reproduced S3K steady-state results within 0.5% discrepancy for most parameters, illustrating close agreement in steady-state initialization. Key safety parameters, such as maximum nodal fuel enthalpy, generally remained within 4% difference relative to S3K, while the largest steady-state difference, observed for core pressure drop, stayed below 7%, attributable to differences in core inlet flow-splitting treatment between the two codes. During transients, most deviations for major parameters were within 5–10%, with the PP scheme showing better overall agreement than FP. The FP scheme exhibited unexpectedly larger discrepancies in core pressure drop, which cannot yet be fully explained but are likely related to flow redistribution effects; further investigations are required to clarify these variations. Overall, the S5K core-only model reliably reproduces the core thermal-hydraulic behavior of S3K, with deviations reasonably understood. These results support extending S5K to include peripheral systems and further validation against plant data.

Keywords: SIMULATE-3K, SIMULATE5-K, Transient Analysis, Verification and Validation, KKL

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past several years, Axpo has employed the best-estimate transient code S3K [1] to model transients for KKL. The code has supported dynamic analyses of anticipated operational occurrences (AOOs) and accident scenarios, provided independent verification of Reload Licensing Submittal (RLS) evaluations, and contributed to scoping studies for KKL.

SIMULATE5-K (S5K) [2] is Studsvik Scandpower's (SSP) next-generation best-estimate transient code, extending the capabilities of the steady-state code SIMULATE5 (S5) to transient conditions. The main motivations for its development are to modernize the existing S3K code and to ensure fully consistent solutions between steady-state calculations and transient initialization.

More recently, Axpo has adopted S5K as the future reference tool for reactor transient analyses. As the code continues to undergo refinement and performance optimization by the code developers, Axpo has

initiated a comprehensive verification and validation (V&V) program to rigorously assess its capabilities and ensure readiness for future deployment.

As an initial step in this program, the present analysis focuses on evaluating the KKL S5K core-only model. The primary objective is to compare its performance against the established S3K model, thereby building confidence in the accuracy and reliability of the newly developed S5K model. Beyond this comparison, the study will provide valuable insight to support the transition toward a full model that includes the plant's peripheral systems, by enabling clear isolation of vessel-related from core-related effects.

The assessment is based on two transient scenarios drawn from the series of cases routinely analyzed as part of the KKL yearly RLS evaluations. It should be noted that the current objective is not to compare S5K with plant measurements, but rather to benchmark the S5K core-only model against S3K. Validation against plant data will follow once the full S5K model, including the vessel and peripheral systems, is available.

2. METHODOLOGY

In this study, nuclear data were generated with the lattice code CASMO5 and processed by the linking code CMSLINK5 into a library used by the nodal codes S5, S3K, and S5K.

A consistent methodology was applied to initialize the S3K and S5K core models (*Figure 1*). Steady-state S5 calculations were first performed for the exact operating conditions of each transient, using restart files generated with the CASMO5-SIMULATE5 (CMS5) reference models of Axpo. These runs employed the EPRI-Lahey models for void and subcooled boiling and the Martinelli–Nelson correlation for the two-phase friction multiplier, ensuring consistency with S3K, which uses the same correlations. The resulting steady-state data were then transferred to both S3K and S5K via restart files, providing identical initial conditions for each transient simulation.

Figure 1. S3K and S5K Models Initialization Methodology

Subsequently, each transient was simulated using the complete S3K model, i.e. core and peripheral systems, to extract boundary conditions for the S5K core-only runs. These conditions include time-dependent total core inlet flow and inlet and exit core pressures. It should be noted that the S3K model

was enhanced by adjusting the inlet orifice loss coefficients, as proposed in [3], which effectively reduces discrepancies between S3K and S5K, particularly for core pressure drop predictions.

The S5K core-only model is run, using two core hydraulic boundary condition (BC) types based on S3K, called PRESSURE-PRESSURE (PP) and FLOW-PBAL (FP). The current analysis has been conducted in full compliance with SSP recommendations [4].

In both schemes, the time-dependent outlet pressure is prescribed. In the PP case, the inlet pressure is also supplied, and S5K computes the inlet and channel flows to satisfy the core pressure drop. In the FP case, the time-dependent inlet flow is supplied, and the radial flow distribution is iterated to balance the pressure drop. In both cases, the split between active channels, water rods, and bypass is determined.

The implementation of S3K BCs in the S5K core-only model proceeds as follows (e.g. PP case):

1. Run the full S3K model and extract time-dependent inlet and outlet pressures.
2. Supply these pressures as BCs to the S5K core-only model.
3. S5K computes steady-state values¹ of inlet and outlet pressure from the given operating conditions.
4. Transient inlet and outlet pressure variations, from S3K, are superimposed onto the initial steady-state values.
5. At each time step, there are two iterations in S5K:
 - a. Inner iteration:
 - i. Core flow is estimated based on core inlet/outlet pressure
 - ii. Flow distribution is computed
 - iii. Core pressure drop is computed
 - iv. Core inlet pressure is computed
 - b. Outer iteration:
 - i. If inlet pressure from (a.iv) agrees within tolerance with that from (a.i), proceed to next time step.
 - ii. Otherwise, adjust core flow and repeat steps (a.ii-a.iv) until convergence.

3. DESCRIPTION OF ANALYSED TRANSIENTS

In this paper, two transients, one classified as an AOO (Anticipated Operational Occurrence) and one as an accident, are selected for analysis among a series of transients simulated annually within the framework of the KKL RLS (*Table I*). These are: the Generator Load Rejection without Bypass, referred to as LRNBP, representing events resulting in significant increase in reactor pressure, and the Fast Run up of Two Recirculation Pumps, called also Fast Core Flow Runout with Two Recirculation Pumps,

Table I. Transients' Initial Operating Conditions.

Transient	Cycle Point	Power (%)	Flow (%)	Feedwater Temp (C)	Dome Pressure (bar)
LRNBP	BOC	25	80	158.8	66.7
FCFR2	BOC	100	108	222.8	73.1

¹ Known as steady-state initialization

referred to as FCFR2, representing events resulting in large increase in core flow rate.

A brief description of the two transients, analysed in this study is provided below.

3.1. Generator Load Rejection without Bypass

This event is initiated by a sudden disconnection of the generator from the electrical grid, leading to closure of the turbine control valves (TCVs). The turbine bypass system is assumed inoperable, preventing immediate steam pressure relief. As a result, reactor pressure and neutron flux increase rapidly. A reactor scram is initiated on high pressure, and safety/relief valves (SRVs) open to limit the pressure rise. No early scram on TCV closure occurs if reactor power is below 40% (which is the case here), in accordance with protection system logic. This scenario challenges the pressure control system and credits the performance of the high-pressure scram and SRVs in the absence of bypass operation.

3.2. Fast Run up of Two Recirculation Pumps

This accident is initiated by a malfunction in both frequency converters, resulting in maximum torque being applied to the recirculation pump motors. This causes a rapid increase in pump speed, leading to a swift rise in core flow and reactor power. The power increase triggers a reactor scram on high neutron flux. Core flow is ultimately limited by the maximum torque available from the pump motors. In this scenario, the Class 1E overspeed protection system is not credited, as the initiating event assumes loss of 1E power, rendering it inoperable.

4. RESULTS

The S5K solutions are compared to those of S3K in terms of six parameters of interest: inlet and outlet core pressure; core total power and inlet flow; core pressure drop; and maximum nodal fuel enthalpy.

The difference in results between the two codes is also evaluated. It should be noted that, in all the figures below, the labels Diff1 and Diff2 in the legend represent the relative differences between the S5K model results, using the PP and FP boundary conditions, respectively, and the corresponding S3K results.

For all the simulations, a time step of 0.020 seconds is used. In the S5K model, based on PP hydraulic BCs, the time-dependent inlet and outlet core pressures are supplied from the S3K calculation, while in the other model, based on FP hydraulic BCs, the time-dependent core inlet flow and outlet core pressure are supplied from the S3K calculation. The two models are referred to as S5K-PP and S5K-FP, respectively, in all the figures.

4.1. Generator Load Rejection without Bypass

In this transient, the SCRAM is triggered when the steam dome pressure exceeds the plant specific limit. In S3K, this is modeled with a pressure-based trip, which functions only when the BWR peripheral system is active; hence, the trip is correctly triggered in S3K but not in the core-only S5K model. To address this, a time-based trip is applied in S5K, with SCRAM triggered at the time S3K first exceeds the respective threshold, including a delay for control rod insertion.

Results of this scenario are illustrated in *Figure 2-Figure 3*. Each figure shows the time-dependent parameter of interest calculated by both codes and the associated differences.

The correctness of the boundary conditions implemented in S5K, derived from S3K, can be assessed by comparing the core inlet and outlet pressure and the core inlet flow profiles (*Figure 2*). For the PP model, the initial discrepancies relative to S3K are about 0.30% for inlet pressure and 0.23% for outlet pressure. These differences stem from modeling approaches in the two codes rather than from the BCs themselves. Over the transient, the inlet pressure deviation remains within 0.25–0.30% and the outlet within 0.18–0.24%, both considered very small. In the FP model, the inlet flow shows zero discrepancy because it is directly imposed as a BC, while the outlet pressure discrepancy remains similar to that of the PP model (0.18–0.24%). Conversely, for core inlet and outlet pressures, it is the change in these parameters that is imposed, leading to the observed minor discrepancies. Overall, the comparisons confirm that both S5K models implement the boundary conditions correctly, with only negligible deviations from S3K.

Results of core inlet flow with PP BCs show a close agreement with those of S3K at the start of the transient, with deviations gradually increasing to less than 1 % by the end of the transient.

Figure 2. S5K/S3K Comparison - LRNBP: Inlet and Exit Core Pressure, and Total Core Flow

Figure 3 presents the results of total power, core pressure drop, and maximum nodal fuel enthalpy. For total power, both S5K models show close agreement with S3K at the beginning and end of the transient. Throughout the transient, deviations generally remain below 5 %, except during the rapid power decrease, where the discrepancy increases to approximately 14 % for both models. This deviation is attributed to a slight time-shift between the curves during the steep power drop.

Figure 3. S5K/S3K Comparison - LRNBP: Total Power, Core Pressure Drop and Nodal Fuel Enthalpy

For the core pressure drop, both S5K models start with a deviation of about 5 % from S3K. During the transient, the PP model maintains a deviation close to its initial value, whereas the FP model’s deviation increases to roughly 16 %. The cause of this larger discrepancy is not yet fully understood, particularly given that the core flow deviation remains nearly negligible, but is most likely linked to flow

redistribution between the bypass and active zones. Further investigation will be required to confirm this explanation.

Finally for the safety-relevant parameter, i.e. maximum nodal fuel enthalpy, results show close agreement between the two codes, with an initial deviation about 1%, remaining below 2.5% throughout the transient.

4.2. Fast Run up of Two Recirculation Pumps

Results of this scenario are presented in *Figure 4-Figure 5*. Each figure shows the time-dependent parameter of interest calculated by both codes and the associated differences.

The correctness of the boundary conditions in S5K, supplied from S3K, is assessed through the core inlet and outlet pressure profiles and the core inlet flow (*Figure 4*). For the PP model, initial discrepancies with S3K are about 0.7 % at the inlet and 0.54 % at the outlet, similar to the previous transient scenario. These deviations remain very small and stable over time (0.7–1.0 % and 0.54–0.75 %, respectively). In the FP model, the core inlet flow shows zero discrepancy, as it is directly imposed as a boundary condition, while the outlet pressure discrepancy is comparable to that of the PP model. Overall, both S5K models demonstrate correct implementation of the boundary conditions, with negligible differences from S3K.

Results of core inlet flow with PP BCs show good agreement with S3K throughout the transient, with the maximum deviation remaining below 1.5 %

Figure 4. S5K/S3K Comparison - FCFR2: Inlet and Exit Core Pressure, and Total Core Flow

Figure 5 presents the results of total power, core pressure drop, and maximum nodal fuel enthalpy. For core power, both S5K models remain in close agreement with S3K over most of the transient. A peak deviation of approximately 30 % for the PP model and 45 % for the FP model is observed at about 2.5 s, likely attributable to a time shift between the power peaks in the two codes.

For core pressure drop, both S5K models initially deviate from S3K by about 7 %. As core flow increases, the PP model remains near this level, whereas the FP model's deviation rises sharply, reaching a maximum of approximately 25 %. Again, the underlying cause of this larger discrepancy remains unclear, particularly since the core flow deviation appears to be nearly negligible; but it could be related to flow redistribution between the bypass and active zones. Therefore, further investigation will be required in future work.

For the maximum nodal fuel enthalpy, results show a close agreement between the two codes for this safety-relevant parameter at the start of the transient, with initial deviations of about 1 %. As the

transient progresses, deviations in the PP S5K model remain below roughly 3 %, while in the FP S5K model reach a maximum of about 5.5 %.

Figure 5. S5K/S3K Comparison- FCFR2: Total Power, Core Pressure Drop and and Nodal Fuel Enthalpy

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

A comprehensive assessment of the KKL S5K core-only model was performed through detailed comparisons with the established S3K model, based on two representative limiting transients for KKL.

Transients were first simulated with the full S3K model (core, vessel, and steam lines) to extract boundary conditions for the S5K core-only model. S5K was then run with two types of hydraulic boundary conditions (PP and FP). In both, a time-dependent outlet pressure change is applied; in the PP case, a time-dependent inlet pressure change is also provided and flow is calculated to match the pressure drop, while in the FP case, a time-dependent inlet flow is imposed and radial flow is balanced accordingly.

The comparison of results from the two S5K models (PP and FP) against those from S3K shows overall good agreement. A summary of the findings, including additional parameters such as bypass flow, exit flow and enthalpy, and maximum nodal centerline fuel temperature, is presented below and illustrated in *Figure 6*. The figure displays the relative differences at the beginning of the simulation, reflecting the steady-state initialization of each model, and at the point of maximum deviation between S5K (PP or FP) and S3K results. As shown, at the onset of all transients (*Figure 6*, left), both S5K models reproduce identical initial values for all parameters, as expected, since these are determined by the provided operating conditions and are independent of the boundary conditions. In addition, both scenarios show a similar range of discrepancies across all parameters. More specifically, both S5K models align very closely with S3K for total power, core flow, bypass flow, and core exit flow, with discrepancies generally below 0.5%. For core-exit enthalpy, maximum centerline fuel temperature, and maximum fuel enthalpy, deviations remain within about 3%. The largest deviation occurs in the core pressure drop, remaining below 7%. This level of discrepancy between S5K and S3K is consistent with earlier observation [3] and is mainly attributable to differences in the treatment of inlet flow splitting: S5K employs a detailed flow-splitting model, whereas S3K represents the bypass with a single channel and only the active flow passes through the orifices.

Focusing on maximum deviations during the transients (*Figure 6*, right), the overall agreement is good. For most parameters, deviations between the S5K models and S3K stay within 10%, often below 5%, with the PP model consistently showing lower deviations than the FP model, particularly for total power and core pressure drop. The largest PP model deviation occurs in total power during FCFR2

($\approx 30\%$), while the FP model reaches a peak deviation of about 45%. For the FP model, core pressure-drop deviations rise significantly, reaching $\sim 25\%$ in FCFR2, despite negligible differences in total core flow. This behavior cannot be fully explained but is most likely linked to flow redistribution between the bypass and active zones, although further investigation is required to clarify the increase in pressure drop under these boundary conditions.

More importantly, for key safety-related parameters, namely maximum nodal centerline temperature and enthalpy, as well as core exit flow and enthalpy, both S5K models show strong consistency with S3K. This provides confidence in the ability of S5K to reproduce system behavior across a wide range of transient conditions.

Figure 6. Initial and Maximum Deviation between S5K and S3K

In conclusion, the comparison shows close agreement between the S5K core-only model and the established S3K model, supporting confidence in the S5K KKL model across the analyzed transients. This consistency confirms that the core-only model replicates core behavior adequately, providing a solid basis for extending it to include peripheral systems and for distinguishing core- and vessel-related effects. A detailed verification and validation against plant measurements will be conducted once the complete S5K model is finalized.

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